

TAX DISCIPLINE IS A FACTOR OF BUDGET STABILITY

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In this study, the tax culture and tax discipline were investigated, because the economic potential of the state is built on the basis of its financial security. Therefore, the high tax culture of the population determines the future of each country, and in this context, we have determined the study and discussion of the factors in the formation of the tax culture and tax discipline of the population as the main goal of this research.

Key words: taxation, tax culture, deviant behavior, taxpayers, tax burden, tax law, tax authorities, tax employees.

A person's moral qualities should not be judged by his personal actions, but by his daily life. To date, tax illiteracy is one of the most discussed problems of economic development not only in our country, but also in the whole world. Unfortunately, at this stage of society's development, this indicator is low, due to various reasons: a large part of the population does not have basic education, lack of computer technology and Internet resources for the population, ignorance of changes in tax legislation, etc. In turn, low tax literacy causes a number of problems, such as the development of the underground economy, the low level of revenues to the

budget, the emergence of tension in the social environment, the instability of the regional economy, and others.

Therefore, having legal knowledge, knowing about your rights and opportunities to receive tax benefits is a necessary condition for the development of the region.

Often using the concept of "tax literacy", they also affect tax culture. Tax culture includes knowledge and skills of citizens, as well as cultural and moral qualities, values and standards. Therefore, tax culture is a broader concept than tax literacy¹⁰.

We know that taxes are the main source of state budget revenues⁶. Thus, the main factors of increasing budget revenues today are the creation of a healthy competitive environment, ensuring the necessary level of collection of taxes and other mandatory payments, legalization of the activities of persons operating in the underground economy, and voluntary fulfillment of tax obligations by taxpayers.

Taxation is, in fact, universal; therefore, the participants of this process are not only representatives of tax authorities or employees of organizations, but also the entire population - taxpayers (real and potential), who demonstrate various forms of tax behavior. The widespread use of deviant forms of tax behavior related to the violation of the tax payer's obligation to pay taxes established by law in our country indicates serious systemic reasons that support this attitude of the population to the law and their duties.

Taxation is an evolutionary process that largely depends on the level of tax culture, which mainly determines the formation of tax behavior of all its participants. Tax behavior of the population is determined by value orientations, including legal

norms, motivations, customs, traditions and customs, which directly affect the formation of tax culture..²

Tax culture is a complex socio-economic phenomenon characteristic of a society with a market economy, and its level determines the fiscal position of the state. There is no single approach of scientists to define the concept of "tax culture", because in fact, each research on tax topics depends on certain conditions and territorial location. Speaking about regional location, we should remember the initiative of our president: "First of all, new approaches will be introduced to reduce economic inequality between regions and develop all districts and cities at the same time. We did a thorough analysis. Starting next year, districts and cities will be divided into 5 categories based on their existing conditions, potential and opportunities. In particular, 26 districts that are comprehensively developed for entrepreneurship

- category 1; 46 districts with good infrastructure
- to category 2; 76 districts with relatively satisfactory conditions
- to category 3; 40 districts with insufficient attractiveness
- to category 4; 20 districts with difficult conditions belong to the 5th

category. Now, depending on the category, we determine the economic development of the districts. Subsidies, loans and compensations for entrepreneurs are allocated based on categories. Tax rates will be different for them" – Mirziyoyev Sh..¹

The above considerations once again determine that the tax culture depends on the territorial location and approach, according to B. Nerre, his classic concept in a certain country is primarily the creators of the tax system³. Taxpayers were not considered part of the tax culture. For the first time, the definition of "tax culture" was used in the article "Economics and Sociology of Income Tax" by J. Schumpeter,

who said that tax culture is an expression of human spirituality and creativity aimed at raising the level of society's tax consciousness⁴. The effectiveness of the tax administration consists of the state of the tax system, its integrity, stability, fiscal and economic efficiency. It depends on the stability of filling the country's budget system with tax payments, the timely implementation of detection and prevention of tax violations and the provision of favorable conditions for taxpayers to fulfill their constitutional duties.⁵

Growth has been achieved in all types of taxes, which means that together with the activities and measures taken by the state tax authorities, it can be said that the growth of the culture of taxpayers and the harmony of cooperative relations have created the basis for this.

Executive authorities, the government as a whole, should not be limited to the goal of financial stability during their management, and should also take into account their perspectives and long-term consequences of their decisions. In the field of tax policy, this requirement is expressed in the clearest form: the tasks of collecting current taxes should always be clearly related to the tasks of maintaining and increasing the future tax base of the state.

After all, an integrated approach to solving all these problems is the key to a correct understanding of the basic postulates of tax culture and the principles of correct taxation at all levels of society and at all levels of public administration, as well as a healthy and effective fiscal policy of any modern state⁷.

An important element of tax culture is tax discipline. Tax discipline of citizens is the main element of tax culture and the basis of tax literacy of the population [8], [13], [14]. Tax discipline is an integral part of the tax culture and

determines the attitude of citizens to their obligations to pay taxes to different levels of budgets as defined by law. ^{[9], [11], [12]}.

However, in today's world, many taxpayers are trying to find ways to avoid their tax obligations in one way or another. This behavior can be explained by a person's propensity to save and his reluctance to share the results of his work with others, especially with the state, and the nature of taxes.

In our opinion, the process of formation and improvement of tax discipline takes a long time and faces many problems, which may be caused by: - imperfection and frequent changes in tax legislation; - citizens were not given enough advice on tax issues, as well as conducting advertising and information events, using media channels; - lack of public trust in tax authorities; - poor performance of tax procedures; - insufficient motivation of public service employees; - quick turnover of personnel in tax authorities; - the growth of competition between companies, which leads to the use of methods of reducing the tax burden by economic entities.

In our opinion, it will be good to mitigate the above-mentioned problems and implement the following as a solution: First, the tax culture formation program should be aimed at the younger generation, which aims to understand the social necessity and economic benefits of taxes. A training course on the basics of tax knowledge should be included in the school curriculum.

Secondly, it is necessary to improve the efficiency of tax services so that taxpayers have a positive opinion. It is necessary to introduce wide use of electronic databases and tax consulting services with the help of Internet resources.

Thirdly, in order to reduce the number of misinterpretations of the tax legislation, it is necessary to eliminate all loopholes and ambiguities in the tax code, to make the presentation language more convenient for taxpayers.

Fourthly, tax service employees must perform their work conscientiously and at a high professional level, observe impartiality, ethical standards and rules of conduct. Tax authorities should be correct and attentive to the problems of taxpayers, show them tolerance and respect.

Thus, the problem of forming a tax culture remains as urgent as ever. This process is long, but it is very necessary for our country. Tax authorities and taxpayers must have important common interests that can be used to comply with tax laws and create an environment conducive to economic growth in all areas of business and the development of the country as a whole.

As I noted in my dissertation that I defended in 2016, "...legal advocacy in the field of taxation deserves a positive assessment. It is certainly gratifying that thousands of citizens will participate in these events. But "you need to work for the result, not the process." This should definitely be considered.

For example. "What was the result?" to the hunter returning from the hunt. if you ask, he will say: "We walked 10-12 km, we waited for the prey, we fired 47 shots. It's good, thank God," he says. "I shot 2 hares and 4 partridges," he says.

The doctor also said: "I had 10 patients. For two weeks, I diagnosed them, gave them injections, checked their condition twice a day, and carried out the necessary procedures," he said. He says: "In one week, 6 of them got better, and I am treating 4 of them."

And the farmer says that he collected 40 centners of first grade cotton per hectare and sold it to the state, not because of how many times he watered his cotton, how many local fertilizers he applied, and how many times he cultivated.

A fighter is also rewarded not by how many shots he fires at the enemy, but by how much he reduces the enemy, and others ..."¹⁷

The urgency of solving the problem of ensuring a high level of tax culture and discipline is confirmed by the paradoxical situation where the society itself provokes deviant behavior or its hidden propaganda. Thus, the lack of targeted concepts of increasing tax literacy and creating a tax culture among the masses has led taxpayers to view tax evasion and even evasion as heroic. Even well-known tax advisors publish tax evasion techniques in the general press, and the more they offer, the more qualified a professional they are.

Tax culture generally performs the following functions: 1) cognitive-prognostic; 2) humanistic; 3) regulation and regulation; 4) subject-practical; 5) reflexive and creative.

Tax culture is understood not only by every scientist, but also by every participant in tax relations. Thus, some consider tax culture to be a relatively narrow concept: only the level of responsibility of the taxpayer and his tax consciousness. Others believe that this concept is much broader and includes not only the tax-legal consciousness of the society, but also the formal and informal institutions of the state, since only one party cannot participate in any relationship, including taxation. Parties interact with each other, and the effectiveness of this interaction determines the outcome of the relationship.

Thus, the tax culture is manifested not only in different tax behavior of the taxpayer, but also when some taxpayers bear the full tax burden, and some minimize it by legal (tax optimization) and illegal methods (tax evasion). Tax culture is also manifested in relations with tax authorities, when taxpayers collude with tax officials, which contribute to the development of deviant behavior of taxpayers. Thus, the tax culture covers both the activities of taxpayers and the activities of tax authorities in close cooperation with each other.

The science and practice of tax law confirms the connection between the legal understanding of tax relations and their implementation, which emphasizes the need to have comprehensive knowledge of tax and other legal documents for the implementation of universal values ^[15], ^[16]. Therefore, tax culture applies to both taxpayers and regulatory bodies in the field of taxation. For individuals and legal entities, it depends on civic loyalty under fiscal pressure, and for tax officials, it depends on professional competence and moral and ethical compliance with their duties.

Thus, in our opinion, the most important element of tax culture is tax discipline, which is related to regular preparation, development and control of the taxpayer's moral, financial abilities and capabilities to pay with the budget system, and is determined by the synchronicity of the relationship between tax authorities and taxpayers. It means that the scope of the concept of tax culture includes both the activities of taxpayers and the activities of tax authorities. Therefore, this activity should be considered together. On the one hand, the culture of the tax authority and its officials has a major impact on the taxpayer's behavior, creates additional pressure or incentive points, on the other hand, taxpayers exert some pressure on the tax authorities. They base their response on the deviant nature of their behavior (changing credentials, imposing sanctions, conducting unscheduled inspections, warrants).

If this pressure goes beyond the general culture, a conflict arises between the taxpayer and the tax officials. Of course, the conflict situation in the tax authority leads to slow down of tax payment by taxpayers.

In conclusion, it can be said that it is impossible to form the rule of law and form a high-level culture without active, clear, open and wide-scale informing of the

population. Legal information is a necessary condition to prevent legal nihilism among the citizens of the country. Ensuring the coordination and interaction of educational institutions, scientific research institutions and authorities, the activities of the legislative body in establishing law and order, spreading legal knowledge, as well as the practice of tax consultants, auditors, legal clinics, legal associations and legal aid centers should contribute in general. Forming a positive image of tax authorities should improve the state's relations with taxpayers, form civil responsibility for all sides of this cooperation.

Also, in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Advertising", mass media, outdoor advertising and information distributors are required to post social information in the amount of not less than five percent of the total monthly volume of airtime, publication or advertising space allocated for advertising. being This number should be increased to 25 percent.

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